

HIGH-TEMPERATURE ANISOTROPIC THERMAL OXIDATION OF CARBON-FIBER REINFORCED POLYIMIDE COMPOSITES: THEORY AND EXPERIMENT

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ABSTRACT

The individual roles of constituent materials and the fiber-matrix interface in high-temperature oxidation of fiber-reinforced polymer-matrix composites are investigated. Two high-temperature polyimide composites are used in the experimental part of the study. Oxidation of the resin matrix at the fiber-matrix interface is found to govern the composite oxidation; the contribution of carbon fibers is only secondary. The significant increase in oxidation area due to the fiber-matrix interface must be accounted for in the study of high-temperature advanced polymer composites. Microstructural based models have been developed to evaluate the oxidation behavior of carbon-fiber/polyimide composites, and the results are favorable compared with experimental data.

INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber reinforced polymer composites are increasingly being considered for applications in high-temperature environments, because of their advantageous properties. Of special interest are the polyimide-based composites, since polyimides have some of the highest use temperatures, up to 371°C (700°F). In a high-temperature environment, however, the materials may be subjected to oxidation, resulting in severe material loss and changes in the microstructure. Oxidation of a polyimide composite at high temperatures is among the most critical concerns, since it may determine the useful life of the composite. Attempts to understand oxidation of the composite based on oxidative stability of individual constituent phases have been limited. The main obstacle for this is the inherent complexities of the problem, involving the composite microstructure, the anisotropy of oxidation kinetics, as well as the unknown role of the fiber-matrix interface in the oxidation process.

Among different polyimide-based composites, thermo-oxidative stability of carbon-fiber reinforced PMR-15 is most studied. Scola and Vontell [1] have investigated oxidative degradation of several PMR-15/carbon fiber composites during high-temperature aging, and reported that the useful lives of the composites are significantly limited by the oxidation. Bowles and Nowak [2] and Bowles [3] have reported that PMR-15/C6000 composites lose weight at a lower rate than both the fiber and the resin individually, and have ascribed this to a synergistic effect. The results in [2, 3] contradict the findings of Alston [4] and Scola [5], where the composite weight loss is found to be higher than that of the neat-resin. Nam and Seferis [6] have studied a unidirectional bismaleimide/carbon fiber composite, showing that the oxidation rate of a composite may be determined if oxidation rates in the principal material directions are known. The oxidation anisotropy may be attributed to diffusion of oxygen into the material and is recognized to depend on surface characteristics. An attempt to model the surface and interface dependent oxidation process has not been found in the literature.

The objective of this research is to study the nature of high-temperature oxidation in fiber reinforced polymer-matrix composites. Kinetic models are developed to determine the oxidation behavior of a carbon-fiber reinforced polyimide composite based on the individual oxidation data of fibers and the neat resin. The models include oxidation along the fiber-matrix interface, resulting in a substantial increase in the area susceptible to oxidation.

ANALYTICAL APPROACH

OXIDATION MECHANISMS

Oxidation of polymers and carbon fibers are mainly gas-solid reactions, which may be governed by diffusion, reaction or a combination of both. Oxidation products are generally gaseous, and weight loss is a convenient measure of the degree of oxidation. Kinetic models for general gas-solid reactions are available (see, e.g., [8]). In the case of a flat-plate geometry, the total weight loss flux may be expressed as

$$q_1 = K_1 t \quad (\text{for a reaction-controlled process}), \text{ and} \quad (1)$$

$$q_2 = K_2 t^{1/2} \quad (\text{for a diffusion-controlled process}), \quad (2)$$

where, K_1 and K_2 are reaction rates, involving reaction and equilibrium constants, and t is the reaction time. Oxidation may also be viewed as a thermally activated process and described by

$$K = B e^{-\Delta H/RT}, \quad (3)$$

where K is the reaction rate; B a constant; R the universal gas constant; T the temperature; and ΔH the activation energy.

ANISOTROPY OF FIBER COMPOSITE OXIDATION

A unidirectional fiber reinforced composite contains two types of external surfaces normal to the principal material directions (Fig. 1): surfaces parallel to the fibers and surfaces perpendicular to the fibers. Since oxidation is a surface reaction moving from the surface inward along the surface normal, the oxidation is expected to progress at different rates on different surfaces, depending on the surface microstructure. Oxidation of a surface which is parallel to the fibers will progress transversely to the fibers, and is thus termed transverse composite oxidation, or for convenience simply transverse oxidation (or transverse weight loss). Similarly, axial composite oxidation (or simply axial weight loss) will denote the oxidation of a surface with its normal along the fiber axis.

Figure 1. Transversely isotropic composite specimen.

The total isothermal weight loss of a composite specimen may be expressed as

$$\Delta m_{total}(t) = \Delta m_A(t) \frac{A_A}{A_{total}} + \Delta m_T(t) \frac{A_T}{A_{total}}, \quad (4)$$

where Δm_A is the axial weight loss per unit area; Δm_T is the transverse weight loss per unit area; A_A and A_T are the areas of axial and transverse surfaces, respectively; and $A_{total} = A_A + A_T$ is the total composite surface area¹.

MICROSTRUCTURE-BASED OXIDATION MODELS

Microstructure-based oxidation models are needed to evaluate the anisotropic oxidation, based on oxidation of the fibers and the matrix and other microstructural considerations. To understand the role of the fiber-matrix interface in the oxidation process, two cases are considered. In the first case, which is only used as a reference, the fiber-matrix interface is considered impermeable to oxygen. This case is trivial, since only external surfaces of the composite need to be considered. In the first case, the oxidation weight loss, in the transverse or axial directions, may be approximated, using the rule of mixtures, i.e.,

$$\Delta m(t) = \Delta m_m(t)[1 - S_f] + \Delta m_f(t)S_f, \quad (5)$$

where Δm , Δm_m and Δm_f are weight changes per unit area of the composite, matrix and fibers, respectively, at a given temperature; S_f is the area fraction of fibers on the composite surface; and t is the time.

In the second case, considered for the remainder of this section, oxygen is considered to move along the fiber-matrix interface, either through cracks or by diffusion. Assume: (1) no interdiffusion between fibers and the matrix; (2) oxidation of the matrix and the fiber is uniform everywhere; (3) the geometry of the composite remains unchanged, and (4) the amount of weight loss due to oxidation is small.

Transverse Oxidation

Consider oxidation of a transverse composite surface with the external surface the top layer of fibers partially embedded in the matrix as shown in Fig. 2. A representative unit surface element shown in the figure consists of one semi-embedded fiber with a proportional amount of external matrix surface. The maximum distance oxygen needs to penetrate is half the circumference of the fiber, πR , with an average distance, $1/2\pi R$.

It can be easily shown that the ratio of actual matrix oxidation area, A_m , to apparent matrix oxidation area, A_{ma} , for the matrix in transverse composite oxidation is

$$\frac{A_m}{A_{ma}} = 1 + \frac{\pi}{2} \frac{1}{\left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{V_f}} - 1 \right)}. \quad (6)$$

For example, for a typical carbon-fiber/polyimide composite with a 65% fiber volume fraction, the ratio is 7.5, a significant increase in oxidation area. For the fiber oxidation, neglecting any loose fibers on the surface, a similar procedure leads to

¹ The composite surface area is determined by the external dimensions of the composite, and is referred to as the "apparent" or "surface" oxidation area in the formulation. The weight loss per unit area is taken in reference to the apparent area. The "actual" oxidation area denotes an area which may include internal surfaces such as the fiber-matrix interface.

Figure 2. Composite transverse oxidation.

$$\frac{A_f}{A_{fa}} = \pi, \quad (7)$$

where A_f is the actual and A_{fa} is the apparent fiber oxidation area. (Loose fibers may be taken into account by multiplying the A_f/A_{fa} ratio with the number of loose fiber layers above the embedded fiber).

To account for the actual oxidation area, the oxidation area correction factors, (A_m/A_{ma}) and (A_f/A_{fa}) , may be included, leading to the transverse oxidation weight loss, Δm_T , as

$$\Delta m_T(t) = \Delta m_m(t) \left[1 - \sqrt{V_f} \right] \left(\frac{A_m}{A_{ma}} \right) + \Delta m_f(t) \sqrt{V_f} \left(\frac{A_f}{A_{fa}} \right). \quad (8)$$

Axial Oxidation

The axial oxidation of a composite with an oxygen permeable interface is considered here, with the same aforementioned assumptions. Consider a representative unit cell of the fiber composite under high-temperature oxidation (Fig. 3). The axial oxidation is assumed to take place on the external surface and in an active oxidation zone along the fiber-matrix interface with length d_1 measured from the external surface. Along an additional distance, d_2 , at the fiber-matrix interface, oxygen is present by diffusion along the fiber-matrix interface, but the oxygen partial pressure decreases along the length of the zone due to reaction consumption in the oxidative process. At the end of the oxygen diffusion zone, the partial pressure of oxygen has fallen to zero, and no oxidation is assumed to take place beyond this point.

The oxygen diffusion zone is assumed to move along the fiber-matrix interface in a self-similar manner during oxidation. Following the same procedure used for the transverse oxidation, one can show that the ratio of actual to apparent oxidation area in axial oxidation of the composite is

$$\frac{A_m}{A_{ma}} = 1 + 2 \frac{d_1(t)}{R} \frac{V_f}{(1 - V_f)}, \quad (9)$$

Figure 3. Composite axial oxidation.

for the matrix oxidation, and for the fibers one gets

$$\frac{A_f}{A_{fa}} = 1 + \frac{2d_1(t)}{R} \quad (10)$$

The isothermal composite weight change per unit apparent oxidation area in axial oxidation of a composite may be expressed as

$$\Delta m_A(t) = \Delta m_m(t) \left[1 - V_f \left(\frac{A_m}{A_{ma}} \right) \right] + \Delta m_f(t) V_f \left(\frac{A_f}{A_{fa}} \right) + \Delta m_{diff} \quad (11)$$

where Δm_{diff} is the weight loss due to oxidation in the oxygen diffusion zone. The parameter d_1 , as well as Δm_{diff} , must be obtained experimentally.

EXPERIMENTAL APPROACHES

MATERIALS

Two high-temperature polyimide composite material systems were studied: PMR-15/G30-500 and Avimid-N/IM6 unidirectional fiber reinforced composites. PMR-15 was a highly crosslinked amorphous polyimide, and Avimid-N² was a linear amorphous polyimide. The carbon fibers used G30-500 and IM6, both unsized. The PMR-15/G30-500 in the form of composite laminates were obtained commercially. The fabrication processing was followed by an eight-hour postcure at 316°C, which resulted in a T_g of 330°C. The Avimid-N/IM6 composite was also in the form of laminate panels, with an as-received T_g of 365°C. The fiber volume fraction of the PMR-15/G30-500 was approximately 0.65, while that of the Avimid-N/IM6 was approximately 0.67. All panels used in experiments were determined to be void- and delamination-free based on extensive C-scans.

SAMPLE PREPARATION

The composite panels were cut using a water-cooled diamond-plated saw. Different specimen geometries were used to determine the anisotropy of the composite oxidation. The largest specimens had the nominal dimensions of 50.8 mm long and 6.4 mm wide, with the fibers

²Also known as NR-150B2

running in the length direction in one half of the specimens and in the width direction in the other half. The specimen configurations were chosen to meet the desired ratios of the transverse surface area to axial surface area. For the neat Avimid-N resin, the dimensions were 6.4 mm x 12.7 mm x 3.2 mm. The specimens were all hand-polished (down to 600 grit) on all surfaces to obtain smooth surfaces.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Specimens were first dried to constant weights in a vacuum oven, and initial weights were determined upon removal on a micro-balance with 0.0001 g accuracy. In order to study the high-temperature oxidation process, materials were subjected to elevated temperatures in an air circulating oven for different times and changes in weight were recorded. Three test temperatures were chosen: 316, 343 and 371°C. Specimens were removed from the oven after predetermined times to be weighted on the microbalance, and subsequently returned.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Isothermal weight-loss experiments were performed on both the unidirectional PMR-15/G30-500 and Avimid-N/IM6 composites. Since the composites experienced anisotropic oxidation, specimens of various geometries were used to determine the weight losses on the principal (transverse and axial) surfaces. The oxidative weight changes of the PMR-15/G30-500 are shown in Figs. 4 and 5 for the transverse and axial oxidation, respectively. It is observed that the weight loss on the axial surface is consistently larger than the weight loss on the transverse surface at a given temperature. Owing to space limitations, results for Avimid-N/IM6 composite as well as those for the IM6 and the G30-500 carbon fibers and the neat Avimid-N resin are reported elsewhere [8, 9].

Figure 4. Weight loss per unit area due to isothermal transverse oxidation of PMR-15/G30-500.

The experimental transverse oxidation data are now compared with the predictions obtained from the aforementioned analytical model. Observing the data leads to the approximation that the contribution of the fibers to the composite weight loss is negligible, and the terms dealing with the fiber oxidation in the model may be disregarded. Thus, the second term on the right side of Eqn. (8) vanishes and Eqn. (8) may be rewritten as

$$\frac{A_m}{A_{ma}} = \frac{\Delta m_T}{\Delta m_m} \frac{1}{1 - \sqrt{V_f}} \quad (12)$$

The measured Δm_T and Δm_m were then used to determine the oxidation area correction factor in Eqn. (12), and compared to the predictions. The comparison of predictions and experimental data is shown in Fig. 6 for the PMR-15/G30-500. For each data set, a linear curve fit is made, since

the A_m/A_{ma} is predicted to be independent of time and temperature. The fiber volume fraction of the PMR-15/G30-500 composite was 0.65, resulting in an A_m/A_{ma} of 7.54.

Figure 5. Weight loss per unit area due to isothermal axial oxidation of PMR-15/G30-500.

Figure 6. Prediction and measured oxidation area correction factors for transverse oxidation of PMR-15/G30-500 composite.

The predicted oxidation area correction factors for the transverse oxidation is in good agreement with those obtained from the experiments. The experimental oxidation area correction factor for PMR-15/G30-500 appeared to be constant for the 316°C (600°F) case at a slightly higher level than that predicted, while at 343°C (650°F) it drops slightly with time. It should be noted that discrepancies in the PMR-15/G30-500 data were expected, due to the uncertainty involved in reproducing the neat-resin data from the literature. Nevertheless, the transverse oxidation of both composites is well modeled by the proposed approach, and the high oxidation rate of the composite is rationalized by the significant increase in the actual oxidation surface area due to the involvement of the fiber-matrix interface.

The oxidation of the axial composite surface may be analyzed with the oxidation model. Here again, an approximation is made that the contribution of the fiber oxidation to the composite weight loss is negligible, and the terms dealing with the fibers in the model may be disregarded. Assuming the weight loss in the oxygen diffusion zone is negligible, Eqn. (11) may be simplified as

$$\frac{A_m}{A_{ma}} = \frac{\Delta m_A}{\Delta m_m} \frac{1}{1-V_f} \quad (13)$$

In Fig. 7 the oxidation area correction factor for axial oxidation of the Avimid-N/IM6 is shown.

Note that for the axial composite oxidation, prediction of the oxidation area correction factor cannot be made, since the parameter $d_I(t)$ is not known. However, some aspects of the model may still be addressed. From Fig. 7 it is clearly seen that the oxidation area correction factors increase approximately linearly with time, confirming the assumption in the theoretical considerations that the oxygen diffusion zone progresses in a steady-state, self-similar manner. It is further evident from the results that the initial oxidation rate on a composite axial surface is very sensitive to the initial surface and near-surface conditions, as the initial A_m/A_{ma} are seen to vary from 4 to 11. The difference in the initial conditions is likely caused by the specimen preparation, i.e., cutting and polishing, inducing a varying degree of near-surface fiber-matrix damage. Furthermore, from Eqn. (9) can estimate that the value of A_m/A_{ma} from 4 to 11 only corresponds to a d_I of 0.4 to 1.3 times the fiber diameter. This effect is not found for the transverse oxidation, since the damage will only affect the fibers at or near the surface, which would quickly be debonded due to oxidation anyway.

Figure 7. Measured area correction factors for isothermal axial oxidation of Avimid-N/IM6.

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